

ECONOMICS

THE IMPACT OF DEPRECIATION EXPENSES ON FINANCIAL RESULTS FOR LEASE-ACQUIRED ASSETS IN AVIATION ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

In modern times, the role of leasing in the process of acquiring aircraft by airlines is increasing. As a result of the application of International Financial Reporting Standard No. 16 (IFRS 16) entitled “Leases”, assets acquired under leasing agreements are recorded as “right-of-use assets” in the balance sheet of enterprises and depreciation expenses are calculated on the value of these assets. These expenses have a significant impact on the financial results (operating profit or loss) and asset structure of airlines. The study analyzed the reflection of depreciation expenses on assets acquired through leasing in financial statements, their share in operating expenses and their impact on financial results based on the consolidated financial statements of “Azerbaijan Airlines” CJSC and the independent auditor’s report. [1]

Keywords: leasing, depreciation expenses, right-of-use assets, financial results, AZAL.

Introduction. The main production assets of aviation enterprises are aircraft, which are highly capital-intensive. Due to the requirement of large initial investments when purchasing these assets, leasing mechanisms have begun to be widely used. Through leasing, the right to use high-value assets is obtained, while the financial burden is carried out in the form of lease payments over a contractually agreed period. This process enables optimal management of cash flows and contributes to the liquidity and stable strategic operations of aviation enterprises. [2]

Since 2019, with the implementation of the IFRS 16 standard, significant changes have occurred in lease accounting. Accordingly, operating leases have begun to be recognized on the balance sheet as “right-of-use assets” and “lease liabilities”. As a result, depreciation expenses are calculated for aircraft operated through leasing, and these expenses influence the financial results of aviation enterprises. [3]

The main objective of the study is to analyze the impact of depreciation expenses related to assets acquired under lease agreements on financial results and to determine future strategies for the application of leasing by airlines.

Methods. In this study, a comprehensive methodological approach was applied in order to evaluate the impact of the leasing mechanism on financial results. Methods of analysis and synthesis, as well as comparative and structural analysis of financial statements and normative analysis of the IFRS 16 standard, were used. The empirical analysis was conducted based on financial indicators taken from the consolidated financial

statements and the independent auditor’s report of Azerbaijan Airlines, and the dynamics of these indicators were examined for the period 2021–2024.

Accounting and Depreciation of Lease-Acquired Assets. The application of the provisions of IFRS 16 in lease accounting has led to significant structural changes in the financial statements of airlines. In accordance with the requirements of this standard, from the moment a lease agreement enters into force, airlines recognize assets obtained through leasing and the related lease payments in their balance sheets both as “right-of-use assets” and as “lease liabilities”. [4]

A right-of-use asset is depreciated over the lease term or the useful life of the asset, while interest expense is calculated on the recognized lease liability using the effective interest method. As can be seen, lease payments affect financial results in the form of depreciation and interest expenses.

The application of leasing increases the volume of assets and liabilities on the balance sheets of airlines, while also increasing depreciation expenses and significantly influencing the level of operating profit. The growing role of leasing operations in airlines increases the importance of their accurate reflection in financial statements.

Empirical Analysis (Case of AZAL)

Table 1 reflects the dynamics of right-of-use assets, lease liabilities, depreciation expenses, and total assets of Azerbaijan Airlines for the period 2021–2024.

Table 1.

Selected indicators from the financial statements of AZAL CJSC for 2021–2024 (in million manats).

Indicators	2021	2022	2023	2024
1. Value of right-of-use assets	345.6	519.2	303.2	354.3
2. Lease liabilities (long-term)	232.9	330.3	123.0	78.0
3. Lease liabilities (short-term)	50.0	66.3	55.6	118.0
4. Depreciation expenses	127.4	126.7	157.1	206.1
5. Total assets	1,968.3	2,241.2	2,614.9	2,930.7

Source: <https://www.azal.az/az/corporate-information/financial-reports/>

According to the indicators for 2021–2024, right-of-use assets account for more than one quarter of total assets. These indicators clearly reflect the strategic role of the leasing mechanism in the airline and demonstrate that it serves as a key financing instrument for acquiring highly capital-intensive assets.

While total lease liabilities amounted to 282.9 million manats in 2021, this indicator decreased to 196.0

million manats by 2024. The data presented in Table 1 indicate that the main reason for this decline was the more rapid decrease in long-term lease liabilities (threefold) compared to the increase in short-term lease liabilities (2.36 times), which suggests an expansion in the use of operating leasing.

Diagram 1.

Source: <https://www.azal.az/az/corporate-information/financial-reports/>

As shown in Diagram 1, there is a close relationship between lease liabilities and depreciation expenses. In other words, an increase in lease liabilities directly affects the level and growth rate of depreciation expenses. Empirical results confirm that the increase in the carrying value of right-of-use assets plays a significant role in the rise of depreciation expenses. Although the growth rate of depreciation expenses is observed over the years in Diagram 1, fluctuations in lease liabilities, including both increases and decreases, can also be seen. This can be explained by the fact that in recent years Azerbaijan Airlines has relied more on operating leases rather than finance leases when acquiring aircraft. Under an operating lease agreement, the asset re-

mains on the balance sheet of the lessor, while the lessee only pays the lease fee and does not recognize the asset on its own balance sheet.

The data presented in Table 1 also draw attention to the sharp upward trend in depreciation expenses. During the period 2021–2024, these expenses increased by 78.7 million manats, or 61.8%. The main reason for this increase is the recognition of aircraft obtained under lease agreements as “right-of-use assets” in accordance with the requirements of IFRS 16, and the subsequent recording of depreciation expenses related to these assets in the financial statements. This growth trend once again confirms the long-term impact of leasing operations on the cost structure of airlines.

Diagram 2. Growth Rate of Depreciation Expenses for 2021–2024 in Azerbaijan Airlines.

Source: <https://www.azal.az/az/corporate-information/financial-reports/>

Diagram 2 illustrates the dynamics of depreciation expenses, highlighting an increase of up to 1.6 times over the period. The growth in depreciation expenses is associated with the recognition of aircraft acquired through leasing as “right-of-use assets” on the balance sheet. The expansion of the leasing portfolio and the significant share of long-term leases have increased the carrying value of right-of-use assets, which in turn has led to a rise in asset depreciation expenses over the years. At the same time, the continuation of depreciation expenses related to assets recognized in previous years in subsequent periods has become one of the key factors reinforcing the growth rate of depreciation expenses.

Conclusions and Offers

The results of the conducted research indicate that depreciation expenses related to assets acquired under lease agreements have a significant impact on the financial results of aviation enterprises. With the implementation of IFRS 16, the recognition of lease assets on the balance sheet increases the value of both assets and liabilities of airlines, while the calculation of depreciation for these assets leads to a reduction in operating profit.

On the other hand, leasing enables airlines to operate aircraft without making large initial capital investments in highly capital-intensive assets. This mechanism strengthens the liquidity position of companies and allows for more flexible management of the aircraft fleet. Therefore, it is advisable to analyze the impact of leasing on financial results not only from the perspective of increasing expenses but also in terms of revenue growth, strategic development, and sustainable operations of airlines such as Azerbaijan Airlines.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are presented:

- Since the volume and composition of leasing transactions directly affect the financial stability and liquidity of the airline, the optimal balance of the portfolio should be constantly monitored;
- It is important to accurately determine the useful life of the right-of-use assets in accordance with real operational and technical indicators, as this ensures the correct calculation of depreciation costs and financial results;
- The impact of depreciation policy on financial results should be continuously monitored;
- A comparative analysis of the choice of leasing or outright purchase is advisable.

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